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YOUNG INVESTORS AND BRAND IMAGE OF LIC – A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LIC AND BIRLA SUN LIFE INSURANCE

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The Market share of LIC has been declining day by day whereas the market share of private life insurance which continuously giving superior customer services and offer more innovative products have been increasing with a greater pace. One of the reason of declining market share of LIC is that the brand image of LIC is labeled with, old, traditional and conservative sort of image. And young investors find no modern values in association with LIC. Therefore, LIC must make a fresh strategy to design new innovative products and redesign their existing products and advertise and promote in such a way that attract young investors by catering their modern values. Further, LIC needs to recruit younger-smart sales-force which have great essence professionalism, and it should focus on giving superior customer services, and the offices of LIC must be having modern paraphernalia. In this study we have applied paired sample t-test for comparing and analyzing the differences between the responses given for LIC and Birla Sun Life Insurance respectively.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The study is based on the responses gathered through structured questionnaires. The convenient sampling has been used. Sample size of 140 respondents from Delhi NCR region who have Life insurance policy of LIC/and Birla Sun Life Insurance.

Findings- One of the reason of declining market share of LIC is that the brand image of LIC is labeled with, old, traditional and conservative sort of image. And young investors find no modern values in association with LIC.

Limitations- The study has been conducted in Delhi NCR region and the sample are 140, so the results may not hold apt on pan India bases.

Practical Implications: The LIC have to turn them around regarding their modern and professional image, innovative product inclusion and customer relationship Management, which attract the young investors.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical examples of insurance companies which are following modern marketing tactics and also includes literature review about LIC and Private Life Insurance companies, which offers unique innovative products.

Key words: Market-share, Customer services, Brand Image, Promote, Recruit, Professionalism, Sales-force, Paired sample t-test.

INTRODUCTION:

The Indian Insurance Industry has been changing day by day by the entrance of new world player in the insurance battle-field. Since the Government of India open the sector for private and for foreign player through the process of Liberalizing the economy and adopting the Globalization process, by opening of FDI initially by capping up 26% limit of FDI (Now FDI limit 49%).The LIC i.e. Life Insurance Company of India Limited or JEEVAN BIMA NIGAM which in fact, enjoyed decades as monopoly until the initial years of 90s, but LIC has a large number of customer based and has very strong branding in the minds of Indian Customers. People still believed that LIC is the most trusted brand in the insurance sector, may be due to the image of being Public Sector Undertaking. But in the recent past new Private Insurance companies day by day increasing their market share and slowly and slowly the market share of LIC is shrinking day by day, although LIC still is the market leader. The reason of this shrinking of LIC market share is that, young generation people see LIC as Babu-type Organization, they believe that LIC is not as quick as their private competitor are especially in giving services.

India's public sector insurance behemoth Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC), which has over 2.3 crore policy holders, has crossed the Rs 18,00,000 crore net-worth mark, which is more than the total net-worth of all government banks, including State Bank of India.

This also the fact that with customer based of nearly 2.3 crore and collecting largest figure as renewal premium and having the largest market share in Indian Insurance Industry. Similarly, this is also a fact that in the last ten years the market share of LIC has been shrinking. This trend motivates me to find what the reasons of LIC shrinking market share are. Although, LIC still is the Market leader and having largest Market share.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY: The objective of this study is to find whether the LIC has Strong brand image in the minds of young people (18 to 40) years. And whether LIC has failed to proved itself in coping up the modern values and professionalism.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A brand is a distinguishing name and/or symbol (such as logo, trademark, or package design) intended to identify the goods or services of either one seller or a group of sellers, and to differentiate those goods or services from those of competitors. A brand thus signals to the customer the source of the product, and protects both the customer and the producer from competitors who would attempt to provide products that appear to be identical (Aaker, 1991). Brands provide the basis upon which consumers can identify and bond with a product or service or a group of products or services (Weilbacher, 1995). From the customer's point of view, a brand can be defined as the total accumulation of all his/her experiences, and is built at all points of contact with the customer

(Kapferer, 2004). A successful brand is an identifiable product, service, person or place, augmented in such a way that the buyer or user perceives relevant, unique added values which match their needs most closely (Chernatony and McDonald, 1998).

According to Keller (2003a), consumer brand-knowledge can be defined in terms of the personal meaning about a brand stored in consumer memory, that is, all descriptive and evaluative brand-related information. Different sources and levels of knowledge such as awareness, attributes, benefits, images, thoughts, feelings, attitudes, and experiences get linked to a brand and its understanding by the consumer. The brand, in a sense, acts as a credible guarantee for that product .

Grace and Cass (2005) put forth the concepts of brand attitude, brand verdict, brand attitude and brand satisfaction [2]. Brand attitude is the consumer's overall positive or negative disposition toward the brand. Brand verdict is the consumer's decision regarding future service usage (e.g, repurchase or avoid purchase). Brand evidence is the set of brand associations directly experienced by the consumer during the pre-purchase and consumption stage of decisionmaking. Brand satisfaction is the consumer's positive/negative response to the perceived service performance. Of these the easiest to measure is the last, namely brand satisfaction, but that comes after the brand has been has been consumed. The other three constructs are more difficult to measure. Brand equity is a well-known metric in brand management literature. But it can be measured from multiple points of view namely a) customer based b) company based c) hybrid. The view point radically changes the measure of brand equity. Several experts proposed customer based brand equity measures. Keller (1993) gives an elaborate framework (not a scale) to measure customer based brand equity consisting of brand image and brand knowledge e [3]. He conceptualizes brand image as consisting of brand recognition and recall. He defines brand knowledge as the strength, uniqueness and favorability of brand associations. Park and Srinivasan (1994) conceptualize the difference made by the brand name to the product as a measure of its equity [4]. Swait and colleagues (1993) conceptualize "equivalent price" as a surrogate for brand equity [5]. More recently Ailawadi and colleagues (2003) have conceptualized brand equity as the premium a brand can charge above generics [6]. Yoo and Donthu (2001) propose a multi-dimensional consumer based brand equity scale. But they caution that the scale may not be applicable across cultures [7].

or service, allowing the consumer clearly to identify and specify products which genuinely offer added value (Murphy, 1998). Powerful brands provide long-term security and growth, higher sustainable profits, and increased asset value because they achieve competitive differentiation, premium prices, higher sales volumes, economies of scale and reduced costs, and greater security of demand (Temporal, 2000). The Brand "promise" is the essence of the benefits (both functional and emotional) that customers can expect to receive from experiencing a brand's products/services, which reflects the heart, soul, and spirit of the brand (Knapp, 2000). Successful brands are those brands which adapt well to the environment and thus survive and flourish in the long term inspite of competition they face.

An important factor influencing the selection of a brand concept is consumer needs. According to Park et al. (1986), many brands offer a mixture of symbolic, functional, and experiential benefits.

Functional needs are defined as those that motivate the search for products that solve consumption-related problems (e.g. solve a current problem, resolve conflict, restructure a frustrating situation). A brand with a functional concept is defined as one designed to solve externally generated consumption needs. Symbolic needs are defined as desires for products that fulfill internally generated needs for self-enhancement, role position, group membership, or ego identification. A brand with a symbolic concept is one designed to associate the individual with a desired group, role, or self-image. Experiential needs are defined as desires for products that provide sensory pleasure, variety, and/or cognitive stimulation. A brand with an experiential concept is designed to fulfill these internally generated needs for stimulation and/or variety.

A brand essence that is based on emotional and self-expressive benefits provides a higher-order basis for relationships which can be less vulnerable to product-related changes or easily applied to new contexts (Aaker and Joachimsthaler, 2000). A brand's value proposition is a statement of the functional benefits, emotional benefits, and self-expressive benefits delivered by the brand that provide value to the customers. Functional benefits are the most common basis for a value proposition, based on a product attribute that provides functional utility to the customer and relate directly to the functions performed by the product for the customers. Emotional benefits are positive feelings the customer has about the brand and is related to the experience of owning and using the brand. Most functional benefits have a corresponding feeling or a set of feelings. Self-Expressive benefits focus on person's self-concept, aspirations, and provide a way for a person to communicate his or her self-image.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present study is a comparative in nature and focuses basically on primary data about customer responses for Life Insurance Corporation Of India Ltd and Birla Sun Life Insurance in the Delhi NCR region. The study is based on convenient sampling. A well-structured and pretested questionnaire was administered to the respondents for the collection of data. A sample size of one Hundred forty hundred respondents has been taken for the purpose of the study. However, due to the constraints of time and cost, selection of respondents has been restricted only to some parts of the Delhi, New Delhi, Faridabad, Noida and Gurgaon. In the present study a set of six aspects of Brand image which are so close to the modern and professional elements of a brand has been taken. SPSS 16.0 has been used for various analyses for the study. Paired sample t Test has been used in this study to analyze the difference among the responses of LIC and Birla Sun Life Insurance.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Comparative Analysis of LIC and Birla Sun Life Insurance

A paired t-test is used to compare two population means where we have two samples in which observations in one sample can be paired with observations in the other sample. For Example, a comparison of two different methods of measurement or two different treatments where the measurements/treatments are applied to the same subjects.

Here, Twelve responses on Six parameters are taken on the two companies' viz. LIC, and Birla Sun Life.

We applied Paired sample t-test Six pair of responses (LIC and Birla Sun Life) for the responses given for Six parameters for LIC and Birla Sun Life.

Table-1.a

Paired Samples Statistics- LIC ~Birla Sun Life Insurance							
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	LIC-Offices with Modern Paraphernalia	3.7500	140	1.22987	.10394	-.130	.127
	BSL-Offices with Modern Paraphernalia	4.1071	140	1.18562	.10020		
Pair 2	LIC-Advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India	3.9357	140	1.21862	.10299	-.054	.525
	BSL-Advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India	3.9571	140	1.24005	.10480		
Pair 3	LIC--Smart and Professional Sales People/Agents	4.0429	140	1.13715	.09611	-.136	.109
	BSL-Smart and Professional Sales People/Agents	4.2429	140	1.09197	.09229		
Pair 4	LIC-Image of being a company with modern and professional value	4.5786	140	6.22719	.52629	-.188	.026
	BSL-Image of being a company with modern and professional value	4.2071	140	1.06275	.08982		
Pair 5	LIC-Innovative Products	3.5500	140	1.32124	.11167	-.190	.024
	BSL-Innovative Products	4.2071	140	1.11560	.09429		
Pair 6	LIC-Excellent Customer Services	3.9071	140	1.30244	.11008	.219	.009
	BSL-Excellent Customer Services	4.0929	140	1.19288	.10082		

Table 1.b.

LIC Vs Birla Sun Life Insurance			
S.No.	Feature/Factor	Null-Hypothesis	Alternative Hypothesis
1	Offices with Modern paraphernalia	$H_0: \mu_{LIC} = \mu_{BSL}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	$H_1: \mu_{LIC} < \mu_{BSL}$ ("the Mean for LIC with respect to <i>Offices with modern paraphernalia</i> is Less than that of the mean of Birla Sun Life)
2	Advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India	$2H_0: \mu_{LIC} = \mu_{BSL}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	$2H_1: \mu_{LIC} < \mu_{BSL}$ ("the Mean for LIC with respect to <i>advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India</i> is Less than that of the mean of Birla Sun Life Insurance)

3	Smart and Energetic sales People.	$3H_0: \mu_{LIC} = \mu_{BSL}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	$3H_1: \mu_{LIC} > \mu_{BSL}$ ("the Mean for LIC with respect to <i>Smart and Energetic sales People</i> is Less than that of the mean of Birla Sun Life)
4	Image of being a company with modern and professional value	$4H_0: \mu_{LIC} = \mu_{BSL}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	$4H_1: \mu_{LIC} > \mu_{BSL}$ ("the Mean for LIC with respect to <i>Image of being a company with modern and professional value</i> is Less than that of the mean of Birla Sun Life Insurance)
5	Innovative Products	$5H_0: \mu_{LIC} = \mu_{BSL}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	$5H_1: \mu_{LIC} > \mu_{BSL}$ ("the Mean for LIC with respect to <i>Innovative Products</i> is Less than that of the mean of Birla Sun Life Insurance)
6	Excellent Customer Services.	$6H_0: \mu_{LIC} = \mu_{BSL}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	$6H_1: \mu_{LIC} > \mu_{BSL}$ ("the Mean for LIC with respect to <i>Excellent Customer Services</i> is Less than that of the mean of Birla Sun Life Insurance)

Table 1.c

Paired Samples Test (LIC vs Birla Sun Life Insurance)

		Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	LIC-Offices with Modern Paraphernalia - BSL-Offices with Modern Paraphernalia	-.35714	1.81549	.15344	-.66051	-.05377	-2.328	139	0.021
Pair 2	LIC-Advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India - BSL-Advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India	-.02143	1.78510	.15087	-.31972	.27687	-2.256	139	0.007
Pair 3	LIC--Smart and Professional Sales People/Agents - BSL-Smart and Professional Sales People/Agents	-.20000	1.68018	.14200	-.48076	.08076	-2.714	139	0.016
Pair 4	LIC-Image of being a company with modern and professional value - BSL-Image of being a company with modern and professional value	.37143	6.51102	.55028	-.71658	1.45943	2.675	139	0.04
Pair 5	LIC-Innovative Products - BSL-Innovative Products	-.65714	1.88432	.15925	-.97202	-.34227	-4.126	139	.000

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Pair 5	LIC-Innovative Products - BSL-Innovative Products	-.65714	1.88432	.15925	-.97202	-.34227	-4.126	139	.000
Pair 6	LIC-Excellent Customer Services - BSL-Excellent Customer Services	-.18571	1.56208	.13202	-.44674	.07531	-3.407	1390	0.016

Here, it's clear that in each of the above eight pair the absolute value of **t-value** is greater than the critical value (1.96). Since the significance is **0.021, 0.007, 0.016, 0.04, 0.000 and 0.016** , respectively for the Six pairs which is less than **0.05**, so, we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a difference between the two means or the mean value of each variable or element in case **LIC** is Less than **Birla Sun Life Insurance** for each of the statement which give a picture of LIC that LIC is not seen as a modern brand as compared to private Life insurance (Birla Sun Life Insurance).

Table 1.d.

Null Hypothesis	Features/Parameter	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Result
1H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Offices with Modern paraphernalia	-2.328	0.021	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis
2H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India	-2.256	0.007	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis
3H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Smart and Energetic sales People.	-2.714	0.016	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis
4H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Image of being a company with modern and professional value	2.675	0.04	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis
5H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Innovative Products	-4.126	0.000	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis
6H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Excellent Customer Services.	-3.407	0.016	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis
7H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Advertisements that appeal to youth and modern India	8.353	0.000	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis
8H ₀ : $\mu_{LIC}=\mu_{IP}$ ("the paired population means are equal")	Smart and Energetic sales People.	5.544	0.000	Rejecting Null Hypothesis, and accepting corresponding alternative Hypothesis

Therefore, we can say that the Brand perception and brand image of Birla Sun Life Insurance as modern and innovative is stronger than LIC.

Image of being a company with modern and professional value

CONCLUSION:

While LIC has done commendable work, there is still a great deal of scope for bringing in innovative products and distribution channels to tap the market. The Market share of LIC has been eaten by the private life insurance companies, because private life insurance companies is taking care of their customer by properly addressing their issues, their managers and sales people are more professional than LIC and most important thing they innovate in every

aspect of insurance like product innovation, online request and solving customers problems, proper customer relationship management and offices with fine, modern paraphernalia

Therefore, in the light of this study we can say that the LIC must change their way of dealing with customers and make their products more innovative and catchy, recruiting young and energetic sales force, and redesign the interior of their offices, and advertise in a way that shows LIC is an experienced but a modern company. LIC must design new products and redesign the existing product which can impress the young investors.

Limitation and Scope of the Study: This research has been conducted to know the behavioral preferences of young investors towards LIC and Birla Sun Life Insurance, with a sample size of 140 it does not cover the countrywide picture, with a limited time and monetary resources this study is only giving a picture of Delhi NCR. Further, the new research can be conducted on pan India basis with increased sample size across the India, and this pattern can be studied for some more insurance along with LIC.

References:

- Anshuja Tiwari (Dr) & Ms. Babita Yadav (2013)” A Comparative Analysis of Investor’s Risk Perceptions towards Public & Selected Private Life Insurers in Jabalpur District of Madhya Pradesh”- GIAN JYOTI E-JOURNAL, Volume 3, Issue 3 (Jul-Sep 2013) ISSN 2250-348X
- Arora, R. and Stoner, C. (1996), “The Effect of Perceived Service Quality and Name Familiarity on the Service Selection Decision”, The Journal of Services Marketing, Vol. 10, No 1, p. 22– 34.
- Balderjahn, I. (1988), “Personality Variables and Environmental Attitudes as Predictors of Ecologically Responsible Consumption Patterns”, Journal of Business Research, Vol. 17, No. 1, pp. 51–6.
- Bateson, J. E. G. (1989), Managing Services Marketing: Text and Readings, 2nd Edition, Dryden Press, Orlando, Florida. B
- Bhimrao M. Ghodeswar(2008) “Building brand identity in competitive markets: a conceptual model”-Journal of Product & Brand Management- 17/1 (2008) 4–12
- Debasish, S. (2004). ‘Exploring Customer Preference for Life Insurance In India-Factor Analysis Method’, Vilakshan-XIMB Journal of Management, Vol. I, Issue No. 1, pp. 7-15.